

Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Financial Reporting Quality of Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of corporate board characteristics on financial reporting quality of quoted firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined corporate governance mechanisms and financial reporting quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Analyzed the effect of board size on quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Investigate the effect of board composition on quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study adopted *ex-post-facto* research design. Econometric technique involving Descriptive Statistics, Correlation Analysis and The Ordinary Least Square Regression was used for the data analysis. The result of the study revealed that chief executive officer has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual. Board size has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual and that board composition has positive and significant effects on discretionary accrual in Nigeria. The coefficient of determination (R^2) = 0.712561 showed that about 71% of changes in the discretionary accrual in Nigeria is accounted for by the level of corporate board characteristics. This implies that corporate board characteristics variables are one major contributor on discretionary accrual in Nigeria. The F-statistics (19.349696; $p < 0.05$) indicated that all the variables of the model have significant effect on discretionary accrual in Nigeria. The study concludes that corporate governance mechanisms have positive and significant effects on financial reporting quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Amongst the recommendations is that the number of directors as stipulated in code of corporate governance should not be the main concern but let the size be sufficient in terms of skills, knowledge of financial accounting, and experience as these would foster effectiveness and efficiency of the board in ensuring quality financial report. In addition, more non-executive directors should be appointed since it increases financial reporting quality.

Keywords: Corporate Board Characteristics, Financial Reporting, Firms, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Financial reporting quality among firms has been an issue of concern in accounting. It is an important aspect of accounting system of any organization. This is because practice of financial reporting quality promotes transparency, truthfulness, credibility, fairness and accountability of the reported statement of comprehensive income, financial position and others information in annual report for the interest of users. The need for financial reporting quality was necessitated by concern raised about misleading financial reports, especially during and after global financial crisis (Okaili, Dixon & Salama, 2019). High profile

accounting scandals and collapse of corporate firms around the world such as Enron, WorldCom, Xerox, Aldelphia, Tyco, Parmalat, One-Tel, HIH, Cadbury, Africa Petroleum etc (Okaily et al. 2019), have shown the importance of financial reporting quality. Again, the sack of five Chief Executive Officers of banks and some directors by the Central Bank of Nigeria in 2010 have exposed the need to have effective board structure capable of enhancing financial reporting quality in firms (Masoyi, Aliyu, Ebong & Ogere, 2014).

In Nigeria, every corporate organization has two main decision making organs, namely; the Annual General Meeting (AGM) and Board of Directors (BOD) which are vital for the existence of the firm (CAMA, 2004).

Board of Directors is an essential instrument and a central body in the internal corporate governance mechanisms of a firm (DeBoskey, Luo & Zhou, 2019). The board of directors basically is saddled with the responsibility of monitoring management on behalf of the dispersed shareholders and stakeholders of companies. The workability of an effective board of directors depends on its composition or structure like board independence, board expertise, audit committee and board meetings are vital in promoting corporate governance capable of enhancing financial reporting quality. According to Adebisi (2017), the process of financial reporting involves transmitting financial information to the various users; and a quality process would be contingent on the board structure. The contemporary board of director's structure such as board independence, board meeting, audit committee and board expertise are charged towards monitoring the performance of management and ensure that they act according to the best interests of the owners and promote quality financial reporting (O'Connell & Cramer, 2010). Weak board structures may provide an opportunity for managers to engage in behavior that would eventually result in personal gain. Poor board structure gives room for questionable activities, fraudulent dealings that could lead to an inverse effect on the firm (DeBoskey et al. 2019; Ogbechie & Koufopoulos, 2010). Jensen (1993) believes that board structure is an important internal governance mechanism designed by the firm to counter managerial opportunistic behaviors. It gives an overview of the standard of such organization, which also influences its public image and quality of financial reporting to the stakeholders.

In times past, there have been concerns raised on the effectiveness of the board of directors structure in relation to financial reporting quality. However, several studies have been conducted in developed countries in relation to board structure and financial reporting quality (Bradbury, Mak & Tan (2006) in Singapore; Myring & Shortridge (2010) in US; Gois (2014) in Portugal) but few of these studies were conducted in developing countries like Nigeria (Akeju & Babatunde, 2017; Onuorah & Imene, 2016; Uwuigbe, Erin, Uwuigbe, Igbino, & Jafaru, 2017). Their studies in relation to financial reporting quality were basically on banks. Outcomes of their studies were inconsistent and inconclusive due to methodological approach applied like the use of analysis of variance (ANOVA), multiple least square regression and ordinary least square regression (Akeju & Babatunde, 2017 and Echobu, Okika & Mailafia, 2017), hence the need to validate these studies.

Statement of Problem

The main issue that articulated the motivation for this study is the tendency towards unethical and opportunistic behavior that leads to flexibilities within accounting standards for preparers of accounting information to choose accounting methods, policies, and estimates of their choice in order to meet future expectations of companies to reflect. However, they sometimes use this flexibility to distort financial information for self-serving purposes that do not reflect the company's economic reality (Farouk, 2018).

Company characteristics were found to play an essential role in explaining the quality of financial reporting. A firm trait refers to those motivational variables that moderately stick with firms at different levels and overtime (Shehu, 2012, Shehu & Bello 2013).

Postulates that fixed structural characteristics are integral parts of firm characteristics, relating to characteristics dealing with the structure of firms that are most characteristic of the firm. These structural characteristics such as leverage, age, and size affect the quality of financial reporting (Lang & Lundholm, 1993). These include ownership structure, company size, company age, degree of diversification, financial leverage, company profitability and liquidity, institutional ownership, and tangibility. Company

characteristics may be controllable or uncontrollable, internal, or external to the company decision, and could be susceptible to manipulation by managers. Monitoring variables are a subset of corporate governance that is a central theme in empirical discussions about the quality of financial reporting. Evidence has emerged that firms' choices for their internal governance mechanisms may affect the quality of firms' financial reporting, particularly regarding oversight variables such as institutional ownership and board meetings (Karuna, 2009). Performance variables such as profitability, growth, and liquidity are used as common assessment methods for the financial health of companies over a given period; it affects management decisions in general; however, for certain reasons, it is not always possible to maintain such an impressive performance. Therefore, in these circumstances, when companies are not performing well financially, managers may decide to use some discretionary power to manipulate profits in order to achieve certain target profits or to present a more favorable and compelling outcome of their financial reports in order to impress investors, albeit this can result in lower quality financial reporting (Shehu, 2012). Against the backdrop, the study examined corporate board characteristics and financial reporting quality of quoted firms in Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Corporate Board Characteristics

The phrase "board characteristics" is a blend of two concepts: board and characteristics. While the former as stated in Section 334 (1) of the Companies and Allied Matters Act 2004 (as amended), the board of directors (usually referred to as the board) is vested with the duty of hiring managers and administering the activities of the organization. The latter means a typical or noticeable quality of someone or something. Therefore, board characteristics can be defined as one internal corporate governance mechanism, which expatiates on the features of the board. The characteristics of the board include size, independence, diligence, diversity (age, gender, nationality, expertise, educational and functional background), and committee structure (Anderson et al., 2004). The administrative activities of the board involve the duty of overseeing and monitoring the organizations financial reporting process (Anderson et al., 2004). They meet at a scheduled time with the organizations' accountant and external auditors to review financial statements, audit procedures and the internal control system (Klein, 2002) targeted at improving the organisation's performance. Hermalin and Weisbach (2003) see the board as a market solution that helps mitigate the agency problems that befalls most organizations. According to Jenfa (2000), the board is responsible for a company's internal control systems and has the ultimate responsibility for the operation of the company. Boards define the rules for the chief executive officer regarding hiring and firing, compensation plan and provide high-level advice. Vafeas (2000) see boards duty as mainly responsible for monitoring the quality of information contained in financial reports because managers often have their own interest and incentives with regard to managing earnings and potentially misleading stockholders.

Akeju and Babatunde (2017) opined that a board characteristic which is an internal corporate governance mechanism improves financial reporting quality in an organisation. D'onza and Lamboglia (2014) asserted that a board characteristic is a unique monitoring mechanism for detecting and correcting financial statement fraud. This unique feature of the board makes it hard for accountants in an organisation to perpetrate and conceal a financial statement fraud. Cohen et al., (2004) argued that one of the most important functions of corporate governance (both internal and external mechanisms) is to ensure the quality of the financial reporting process; this argument was supported by (Myring & Shortridge, 2010). Ilaboya and Lodikero (2017) reiterated that it is imperative that the board should have some level of integrity and objectivity in the process of carrying out their duties diligently and should also be confidential in matters relating to the board. Fathi (2013) asserted that the quality of financial information is positively related to the quality of the board and the quality of the ownership structure. To this end, this study critically looked at three board characteristics – independence, diversity (Gender diversity) and expertise.

Financial Reporting Quality

According to the IASB, the essential principle of assessing the quality of financial reporting relates to the accuracy of objectives and the quality of the information disclosed in an entity's financial statements. These qualitative characteristics make it easier to assess the usefulness of financial reports, which will also lead to a high level of quality. To achieve this level, financial reports must be truthful, comparable, verifiable, timely, and understandable. Therefore, the focus is on transparent financial reports and not misleading financial reports for users; not to mention the importance of accuracy and predictability as indicators of high-quality financial reporting (Gajevszky, 2015). As defined in the FASB and IASB Conceptual

Framework for Financial Reporting, there are agreed elements of quality financial reporting. Qualitative characteristics of the quality of financial reporting include relevance, truthfulness, comprehensibility, comparability, verifiability, and timeliness. They are divided into basic qualitative characteristics and improving qualitative characteristics. A theoretical explanation for each of these terms emphasizes their importance as qualitative characteristics and

Verdi (2006) defines financial reporting quality as the exact manner in which it shows information regarding a business activity and its anticipated cash flows, with the aim of informing the shareholders about a company's operations. Also, Martínez-Ferrero, Garcia-Sanchez, and Cuadrado-Ballesteros (2013) define financial reporting quality as the faithfulness of information communicated in the financial reporting process. According to Barde (2009), financial reporting entails disseminating accounting information to furnish current and potential users to enable them assess financial position and cash flow potentials of the firm. The primary objective of financial reporting is to provide high-quality financial information concerning economic entities, primarily financial in nature, useful for economic decisions (Financial Accounting Standard Board (FASB), 1999; International Accounting Standard Board (IASB), 2008). Thus, providing high quality financial report gives various users confidence in the directors and management of companies. Good quality financial reporting provides shareholders and other stakeholders in understanding and absorbing the information through financial statements and hence lowering the information asymmetry. Management could disguise the quality of financial reporting more difficult to be understood by investors and other stakeholders, so that they cannot assess future cash flow implications of accounting transactions (Ishaq 2014). The FASB and IASB have provided qualitative characteristics of useful financial information. These include relevance, reliability, timeliness, verifiability, faithful representation, neutrality, consistency and comparability. It therefore implies that any financial statement that possesses the aforementioned qualities could be regarded as high quality financial report and vice versa

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory provides a framework for the study. The agency theory was initiated and traced by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. The rationale towards the theory is that the company is handled by management (executive directors) who transacts as agent on behalf of the principal who own the business (Clarke, 2004). The agent is mandated with power and authority to take decisions that can be of benefits to the organization. Agency theory sees the organization as a link of contracts in which stakeholders to the firm can carry out transactions (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Problems are bound to arise between principal (owners) and agent (management) in the cause of making personal decision on use of productive assets of the firms. Instituting board and respective structure is an attempt to resolve agency problem. The dissimilarity between owners and control promotes conflict of interest (Aguilera, Filatotchev, Gospel & Jackson, 2008). This is because owners believe that managers (executive directors) could take decisions that are favourable to their selfish interest and not the owners' personal gain (Padilla, 2002). Board structure helps to promote agency theory concepts, because the board facilitates monitoring and controlling management of the firms (Fama & Jensen, 1983). Agency theory helps to strengthen the board of

directors in proper governing of the firm and ensuring performance of the organization (Jackling & Johl, 2009).

Empirical Review

Afensimi and Izedomni (2025) carried out a study that examined whether ownership structure of quoted Nigerian firms has relationship with their dividend policy. The study desegregated ownership structure into managerial ownership, institutional ownership and foreign ownership as the independent variables and controlled for firm size and profitability. Dividend policy being the dependent variable was captured with dividend payout ratio. The sample of 70 firms were selected and data covering eight (8) years were collected. The study regressed the model using pooled, fixed effect, random and GMM effect and the Hausman test supported fixed effect model for result interpretation. The baseline results showed that foreign ownership and institutional ownership has significant positive effects on dividend payment while managerial ownership though positive but did not influence dividend. However, it was found that the effect of ownership structure on dividend payment is significantly moderated by profitability. The study thus recommended the adoption of diverse ownership structure has corporate governance model in Nigeria.

Odeleye (2025) did a study that examined the moderating effect of sectorial disaggregation of corporate governance on the dividend payment in Nigeria. Corporate governance was represented by number of independent directors, institutional investors, board size and managerial shareholding while dividend per share captured the dividend policy in Nigeria. A sample of 97 non-financial listed companies in Nigeria were selected for the study. All the sectors in Nigeria were captured into agriculture, automobile, building, brewery, chemical/paints, conglomerates, construction, food and beverages, healthcare, industrial/domestic products, petroleum and printing/publishing sub-sectors. The analysis was performed at both aggregate and sectorial level using the system generalised method of moment estimation technique to accommodate firm level characteristics and manage autocorrelation bias. The results revealed that corporate governance and dividend payment have positive association. This explains that previous dividend, number of independent directors, institutional investors, profits after tax and gross earnings are drivers of corporate decisions and consequently dividend pay-outs in Nigeria. The study posits that mode of operations (proxied by sector classification) are important in explaining the relationship between corporate governance practices and dividend pay-outs in Nigeria. The study therefore suggested that the number of independent directors on the boards of corporate firms and the proportion of institutional shareholding should be increased to improve monitoring.

Oskar and Talavera (2008) examined the relationship between corporate governance practices and dividend payouts in Poland. The study employed the Transparency Disclosure Index (TDI) as main variable and Board structure and procedures, Disclosure and Shareholders as sub-variables of corporate governance. A sample of 110 non-financial companies listed on the Warsaw Stock Exchange between 1998 and 2004 were selected and analysed using the t-test and Wilcoxon ranked test. The results showed that TDI and its three sub-indices significantly positively influenced cash dividend in Poland. The results suggests that corporate governance that protected shareholders in Poland enhanced their powers to extract dividends from firms. On the basis of the agency theory, the study suggested that firms with strong corporate governance standards can easily mitigate agency conflicts from the use of free cash flow for dividends instead of for further investments with a negative net present value.

Kurawa and Ishaku (2014) examined the effect of corporate governance on dividend policy of five selected commercial banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2003 and 2012. Data was collected from the Annual reports and accounts of the sampled banks. A panel data methodology (Random-effect GLS regression technique) was employed for the analysis of data. The results reveal that management equity holding has significant effect on dividend payout ratio, Board size and CEO duality has insignificant effect, while board independence exhibit negative but insignificant effect. It is recommended that since the fundamental purpose of any company is the creation and delivery of long-term sustainable value in a manner consistent with their obligations as a responsible corporate citizen, then the Bank should therefore views corporate governance not as an end in itself but a vital facilitator to

the creation of long-term value for all stakeholders. And to enhance the level of influence of Corporate Governance on Dividend Payout Ratio to higher level in the Nigerian Banking Industry, Management equity holding should be increased as this will make the management to protect not only their interest but the interest of all stakeholders.

Zulfikar, Nofianti, Dwi Astuti, Meutia and Ramadan (2020) carried out a study to examine the role of ownership's concentration as a moderator of the relationship between dividend policy effects and firm value in Indonesia. Price to Book Value (PBV) was used as proxy for firm value and Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) as the dependent variables was moderated with concentration of ownership, size and leverage. A sample of 23 firms generated for a period of five years spanning 2014 and 2018 were analysed using the Moderate Regression Analysis (MRA). The results showed that dividend policy had a positive effect on firm value. As well, firms whose ownership had been owned by families would affect management policies, such as dividend policy. The study implies that business ethics in Indonesia had been weak and thus there is need to strengthen corporate governance in the economy.

Using a time frame covering 2006 to 2014, Ali, Hanming and Ullah (2018) examined the effects of ownership and board structure on dividend smoothing in Pakistani listed banks. The study employed board size, board independence, audit size, CEO-duality, management, foreign and majority ownership as proxies for corporate governance while Speed of Adjustment (SOA) to dividend payment was used as proxy for dividend smoothing. The sample of 19 banks listed on the Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) within a period of 9 years (2006 to 2014) was regressed using random Tobit technique. The principal component analysis (PCA) was employed to develop a corporate governance index. The findings revealed that banks with concentrated and foreign ownership, small size audit committee and less independent boards, show higher levels of dividend smoothing. However, banks have joint positions CEO and chairperson, showed lesser dividend smoothing. The study posits that increased dividends are sound monitoring mechanism for shareholders within a weak corporate governance environment.

Nwidobie (2013) employed a multiple regression model to identify the determinants of dividend policy in quoted firms in Nigeria. 14 factors were incorporated as independent variables as profitability of the firm, cost of paying dividend, stability of earnings, prospects of raising capital from the capital market, shareholders characteristics, shareholders' needs and requests, availability of investment opportunities, growth prospects of the firm, restriction by lenders, market value of the firm, firm policy, rate of inflation, industry declaration rate, industry declaration rate. Naira dividend paid was the dependent variable. The structured questionnaires was administered on 21 (of the 214) quoted firms on the Nigerian stock exchange on dividend policy. The results revealed that complaints of shareholders does not have significant effect on naira dividend paid by the firms. However, it was found that there is an inverse relationship between the needs and desires of shareholders and the naira dividend paid by the firms. The study recommended that institution of good corporate governance structure should be the finest solution to agency problems in quoted firms that would create better decision structure for dividend in Nigerian firms.

Yousaf, Ali, and Hassan (2019) examined the impact of family control on the dividend policy of firms in Pakistan. Data were gathered from 54 family firms and 49 non-family firms for a period covering 2009 to 2016. The study aimed to also investigate the extent to which of family control moderates the impact of firm-specific factors on the dividend policy. The GMM model for panel data estimation is used. The mean difference univariate analysis shows that family firms differ from nonfamily firms based on financial characteristics. The multivariate analysis shows that family firms pay lower dividends than nonfamily firms. On the overall, the study posited that family control, size, and tangibility are the major determinants of the dividend policy in Pakistan.

Awwad and Hamdan (2018) carried out a study to identify the corporate governance variables in the Gulf financial markets, energy sectors and to determine its effects on dividend policy. A sample of 8 energy firms covering a period of 10 years from 2008 to 2017 from six Gulf financial markets: Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirates. The corporate governance was measured using managerial ownership, size of board of directors, independence of board of directors, Duality of CEO

with size, leverage and growth as moderating variables, whereas payout ratio is the dependent variable. The OLS and logistic regressions showed that firms with good governance seek to distribute the profits among shareholders to reduce the conflict of interests and reduce the agency costs. Thus corporate governance has positive and significant effect on dividend policy.

Al-Kahmisi and Hassan (2018) examined the effect of corporate governance on dividend payout policies in Malaysian banks. The study correlated board size, board independence, and CEO duality with dividend yield. A sample of six banks from public listed companies within a period of five years from 2011 to 2015 were used. The correlation and ANOVA results showed that CEO duality and board independence has negative relationship to the company dividend policy. Further analysis showed that board size has no effect on dividend policy. The core recommendation is that the corporate governance level in Malaysia should be improved.

Kajola, Olabisi, Soyemi, and Olayiwola, (2019) examined the effect of proportional representation of female as directors in corporate boards on the dividend policy amongst 19 listed consumer goods and industrial companies in Nigeria covering 7 years from 2010 to 2016. Dividend pay share served as the dependent variable while Proportion of female directors to total board membership and Absolute number of female directors on board were the independent variables controlled by firm size, board size and profitability. The results from Random Effects Generalised Least Squares (REGLS) model revealed that a positive and significant association between the number of women in corporate boardrooms and dividend policy.

Nwidobie (2020) carried a study to investigate the effect of board diversity on the dividend per share of listed nonfinancial firms in Nigeria in both the short and long-terms. Board diversity was disaggregated into proportion of female, male and minority members of the boards of directors. A sample of nine firms for a period of 2010 to 2018 were analysed using multivariate log-linear regression model. The results indicated that increasing the proportion males on the board has positive effect on dividend per share while increasing the proportion of females and minority shareholders on the boards had negative effects on dividend per share both in the short and long-runs. The study posits that shareholders interested in higher dividend per share should appoint more males, and less females and minorities to the board.

Juhmani (2020) evaluated the effect of corporate governance using board characteristics and ownership structure on dividend payout decision of firms Bahrain within 2014 and 2016. The dependent variable was captured as the dividend payout ratio while the independent variables were board independence, board size, frequency of board meetings, blockholder ownership, institutional ownership and managerial ownership. Results from multiple OLS regression that board independence has a significant negative association with the dividend payout decision, and board size has a significant positive association with the dividend payout decision. Other variables including the frequency of board meetings and ownership structure (blockholder ownership, institutional ownership, managerial ownership) did not have significant effect on the dividend payout decisions.

La Ode (2018) investigated the effect of corporate governance on dividend payout ratio amongst publicly listed firms in Indonesia between 2013 and 2016. The specific variables of the study are ownership structure and corporate governance mechanisms on dividend payout ratio using panel data regression model. The findings of the study indicate that board independence, board size, institutional ownership, size and earnings before interest and tax are positive; whereas the CEO duality, managerial ownership, ownership concentration and leverage are in negative relation with dividend payout ratio.

Gap in Reviewed Literature

A study on corporate board characteristics and financial reporting nexus has been done in Nigeria aggregated all sectors in Nigeria (Afensimi & Izedomni, 2019), non-financial firms (Odeleye, 2017, and Nwidobie, 2020), and the banking industry (Kurawa & Ishaku, 2014). The sole study that targeted the consumer goods firms did so in combination with the sister industrial goods sector (Kajola, *at el*, 2019). Nonetheless, the study did not embrace all facets of the corporate governance paradigm as it dealt with on the factors of female involvement of board management like the ratio of female in directorship position, bad the absolute number of female directors. Thus, studies that would be all embracing in examining the

corporate board characteristics that determine financial reporting quality of quoted firms would incorporate other board composition variables as well as ownership structure issues. This is lacking in extant literature in Nigeria.

The study revealed a dearth of distinct empirical studies those targets to find out the effects of firm size on dividend policy. No empirical study has incorporated all the measures of firm size covering asset, sales and stock market dimensions to size determination. More so, the study on liquidity have either employed the current ratio (current asset divided by current liability) or a variant of firms forms of stock. The quoted firms being a well-developed sector in Nigeria, yet highly competitive and thriving, it is expected that investors interested in financial reporting quality would crave for strategies to enhance financial reporting quality of quoted firms in Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted *ex-post-facto* research design. Econometric technique involving Descriptive Statistics, Correlation Analysis and The Ordinary Least Square Regression was used for the data analysis

Model Specifications

The equations and variables used for the study given below are adaptation and modifications from the work of Safdar, Hazoor, Toheed and Ammara (2019)studied the effect of board characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed conglomerate companies in Nigeria.

The model is stated thus:

$$DA = f (CEO, BS)$$

Where,

- DA = Discretionary Accrual
- CEO = Chief Executive Officer
- BS = Board Size

The model was adopted and modified by the inclusion of board composition

$$DA = f (CEO, BS,BC)$$

The Econometric Equation Form of the Model is:

$$FV= \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEO + \beta_2 BS + \beta_3 BC + \mu- - - - -1$$

Where,

- DA = Discretionary Accrual
- CEO = Chief Executive Officer
- BS = Board Size
- BC = Board composition

β_0 and μ are the constant and error term respectively while β_1 and β_3 are the coefficient of corporate board characteristics.

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics result shows the mean (average) for each of the variables, their maximum values, minimum values, standard deviation and the Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics (normality test). Table 1 below, provides the summary of the descriptive statistics of the selected firms.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	DA	CEO	BS	BC
Mean	0.586085	0.333737	0.463986	32.61932
Median	0.610000	0.360000	0.440000	32.06000
Maximum	1.190000	1.200000	0.760000	58.83000
Minimum	0.400000	0.010000	0.230000	19.01000
Std. Dev.	0.279916	0.195375	0.104344	8.801715
Skewness	0.673540	0.936864	1.037788	0.749291
Kurtosis	3.476098	5.109342	4.069279	3.195801
Jarque-Bera	23.90015	93.20049	63.82646	26.74281
Probability	0.000006	0.000000	0.000000	0.000002
Sum	164.6900	93.78000	130.3800	9166.030
Sum Sq. Dev.	21.93889	10.68798	3.048536	21691.65
Observations	30	30	30	30

Source: Descriptive Statistics Result Using e-view 8

The descriptive statistics result shows a mean value of 0.59 for discretionary accrual. The result shows that on the average the selected firms used in the study has positive financial reporting quality on the average within the period under study.

Chief Executive Officer which shows a mean value of 0.33, maximum value of 1.20 and minimum value of 0.01. This shows that chief executive officer is effective in the financial reporting quality of quoted firms in Nigeria.

The result shows that the average of Board Size is 0.463986, maximum value of 0.760000 and minimum value of 0.230000.

The Jarque Bera and its probability which test the level of normality of the data shows that discretionary accrual, chief executive officer, board size and board composition are normally distributed at one percent significant level.

Correlation analysis

In examining the relationship among the variables, the study employed the Pearson correlation analysis; the results are presented in table 2

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

	DA	CEO	BS	BC
<i>AD</i>	1.000000	0.211078	0.282136	0.097123
<i>CEO</i>	0.211078	1.000000	0.097123	0.282136
<i>BS</i>	0.282136	0.145651	1.000000	0.211078
<i>BC</i>	0.097123	0.100016	0.310316	1.000000

Source: E-view 8

The findings from the correlation analysis table 2, shows that discretionary accrual have a positive relationship with chief executive officer, board size, board composition. The positive relationship between discretionary accrual and chief executive officer, board size, board composition indicates that the more the corporate board characteristics the higher the financial reporting quality of quoted firms in Nigeria. Again an increase in the level of corporate board characteristic will improve the financial reporting quality of quoted firms in Nigeria. The result of the correlation analysis indicate the existence of positive relationship between corporate board characteristics and financial reporting quality of quoted

firms, the implication is that an increase in the level of board characteristics will enhance the financial reporting quality of quoted firms of the selected companies

In checking for multi-co linearity the study noticed that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This indicates the absence of multi-co linearity problem in the model used for the analysis and also justifies the use of the Ordinary Least Square.

The Ordinary Least Square Regression

In this section, we provide the benchmark test of the significance of the independent variables in explaining the effect of corporate governance mechanisms and financial reporting quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: DA

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/11/25 Time: 15:27

Sample: 2019 2024

Included observations: 30

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.667553	0.824890	10.809263	0.0260
CEO	0.164745	1.010577	2.163021	0.0058
BS	-0.518247	0.672745	1.770347	0.2183
BC	0.068816	0.039042	2.762604	0.0302
R-squared	0.712561	Mean dependent var		4.676947
Adjusted R-squared	0.655073	S.D. dependent var		7.153306
S.E. of regression	6.953540	Akaike info criterion		6.888364
Sum squared resid	1208.793	Schwarz criterion		7.165910
Log likelihood	-100.7696	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.978837
F-statistic	19.349696	Durbin-Watson stat		2.971283
Prob(F-statistic)	0.006525			

Source: Eviews 9.0

The results from coefficient (0.667553) and the probability value ($p = 0.0260 < 0.05$) showed that Discretionary Accrual which is the dependent variable (Y) is positive: This means that if all the independent, (explanatory) variables (X) are held constant, discretionary accrual as a dependent variable (Y) will grow by (0.667553) units in annual-wide basis.

Chief Executive Officer: The results from coefficient (0.164745) and the probability value ($p = 0.0058 < 0.05$) showed that chief executive officer had positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis: chief executive officer has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual in Nigeria, is accepted

Board Size: The results from coefficient (0.518247) and the probability value ($p = 0.0183 < 0.05$) showed that board size has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual. This means that the alternate hypothesis two: board size has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual in Nigeria, is accepted.

Board Composition: The results from coefficient (0.068816) and the probability value ($P = 0.0302 < 0.05$) showed that board composition has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual. This means that the alternate hypothesis three: board composition has positive and significant effects discretionary accrual in Nigeria, is accepted.

The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.712561$) showed that about 71% of changes in the on the discretionary accrual in Nigeria is accounted for by the level of corporate board characteristics. This implies that corporate board characteristics variables is one major contributor on discretionary accrual in Nigeria

The F-statistics (19.349696; $p < 0.05$) indicated that all the variables of the model (corporate board characteristics variables) have significant effect on discretionary accrual in Nigeria. The Durbin Watson statistics (2.971283) showed that there was no autocorrelation in the model employed.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined corporate governance mechanisms and financial reporting quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This study result of the study showed that chief executive officer has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual. Board size has positive and significant effect on discretionary accrual and that board composition has positive and significant effects on discretionary accrual in Nigeria.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) = 0.712561 showed that about 71% of changes in the on the discretionary accrual in Nigeria is accounted for by the level of corporate board characteristics. This implies that corporate governance mechanisms is one major contributor on discretionary accrual in Nigeria. The F-statistics (19.349696; $p < 0.05$) indicated that all the variables of the model have significant effect on discretionary accrual in Nigeria. The Durbin Watson statistics (2.971283) showed that there was no autocorrelation in the model employed.

The study concludes that corporate governance mechanisms has positive and significant effects on financial reporting quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Amongst the recommendations is that the number of directors as stipulated in code of corporate governance should not be the main concern but let the size be sufficient in terms of skills, knowledge of financial accounting, and experience as these would foster effectiveness and efficiency of the board in ensuring quality financial report. In addition, more non-executive directors should be appointed since it increases financial reporting quality.

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